

Connected Electric Truck Powertrain: Non-Invasive Fault Detection using Ultra-Low Power Edge AI Sensor Network

Akash Kadechkar
 Smart Energy and Industry Dept.
 N Vision Systems And Technologies
 Barcelona, Spain
 akash.kadechkar@nvision.es

Markus Koller
 Power and Renewable Gas Systems
 Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
 Vienna, Austria
 markus.koller@ait.ac.at

Alejandro Labajos
 Embedded Software Dept.
 N Vision Systems And Technologies
 Barcelona, Spain
 alejandro.labajos@intera-group.com

Abstract—This paper presents a non-invasive, real-time fault detection and predictive maintenance framework for Connected Electric Truck powertrain. Leveraging the ultra-low-power ISM330DHCX sensor’s Machine Learning Core (MLC), the system performs on-sensor processing of accelerometer and gyroscope signals using Edge AI and TinyML techniques. Decision Trees (DTs) and an eight-DT based Random Forest (RF) model were employed to classify vibration patterns under varying operating conditions. Five experiments were conducted on electric motor test benches to simulate rotor imbalance and gather data in both normal and faulty states. Vibration signals were first classified into three broader fault categories and then mapped into 12 subclasses using a novel output mapping scheme. Guided by the Design, Implementation, Potential Failure and Functional Failure (DIPF) curve, this framework enables accurate detection of rotor unbalance faults. Experimental results showed that while single-DT models achieved high training accuracies (95–98.42%) but poor validation performance (<50%), the eight-DT based Random Forest with subclass splitting significantly improved generalization, achieving 98.74% validation accuracy. By minimizing power consumption and bandwidth requirements, this on-sensor Edge AI sensor network approach offers a scalable solution for predictive maintenance, with the potential to reduce downtime and maintenance costs by 30–50%. The findings highlight the promise of ultra-low-power intelligent sensing for enhancing the reliability and efficiency of Connected Electric Trucks.

Index Terms—Predictive Maintenance, ISM330DHCX, Machine Learning Core, Random Forest, Fault Detection, Electric Truck, Powertrain, STWIN, Decision Trees, Edge AI, TinyML, Non-Invasive, Ultra-Low Power, Smart Sensors, AI Embedded Sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN modern electric trucks, the complexity of interconnected components and the increasing reliance on advanced technologies create new challenges in detecting and managing faults [1]. The rapid adoption of electric mobility has driven the need for advanced predictive maintenance systems to ensure reliability, reduce downtime and optimize performance [2]. To address these challenges, RHODAS project introduces Decision Support System (DSS) to enhance Connected Electric Truck reliability through predictive maintenance, targeting a 30–50% reduction in downtime and costs [3], [4].

Fig. 1: RHODAS Connected Electric Truck Architecture.

The high-level architecture of the RHODAS Connected Electric Truck powertrain consisting of three-layer supervision and control network as shown in Fig. 1. Local protection layer is implemented in the local converter processor and deals with critical faults requiring an immediate response to prevent damages. Also, some warning flags are generated. Second layer is implemented at gateway level (edge) using non-invasive sensors and deals with fault feature detection. Third layer is implemented at the cloud platform and oversees long-term fault detection and recommendations for fault management DSS [5]. The commercial Electronic Control Units (ECUs) at the local protection layer consist of critical sensors required for control purposes. These sensors are resource-consuming, invasive, inaccessible, and embedded within the ECU, making remote fault detection and prediction difficult. [6], [7]. This creates the need for non-invasive sensors that can be easily installed at the edge level with connectivity for predictive maintenance, as shown in Fig. 1. The proposed predictive maintenance solution can also be scaled to other Electric Vehicles (EVs) that lack internet connectivity by incorporating the gateway and cloud features to such EVs.

II. RELATED WORK

In electric vehicles, focus is on battery and motor health, often via cloud analytics [1], [8]. However, complete dependence on cloud platforms for predictive maintenance is not feasible. An edge-cloud-AI hybrid solution combining the low-latency capabilities of edge computing AI models with the extensive computational power of cloud servers achieves significant improvements in latency, energy consumption and bandwidth usage addressing the key challenges in predictive maintenance [9]. The RHODAS Connected Electric Truck powertrain consists of several components however in this work the main component used for fault detection is an electric motor.

Fig. 2: DIPF Curve: Asset Condition Over Time.

The Design, Implementation, Potential Failure and Functional Failure (DIPF) curve is a modern framework applied in industrial and automotive contexts for lifecycle management. Effective use of this framework can lead to significant cost savings by transitioning from reactive to proactive maintenance strategies, with planned repairs often being 30% to 50% cheaper than emergency fixes [2], [10]. It was learned from the DIPF curve that the early indicators of the predictive maintenance in an working electric motor are ultrasonic sound and vibration as highlighted in the DIPF Curve Fig. 2. Accelerometer based predictive maintenance are widely used in different applications [11], [12]. The state of the art in on-sensor machine learning for predictive maintenance and related applications has advanced significantly in recent years, particularly with the ISM330DHCX sensor's Machine Learning Core (MLC) enabling energy-efficient edge AI [13]–[15]. The ISM330DHCX supports vibration monitoring in Industry 4.0 [16], but its use in electric trucks is rare. Machine Learning (ML) algorithms like Random Forests (RF) are common in predictive maintenance, but on-sensor implementations are limited by hardware constraints [17], [18]. Therefore, this paper focuses on deploying non-invasive, ultra-low power AI embedded sensor i.e. ISM330DHCX to enable predictive maintenance of the electric motor at the Gateway level. Our work differentiates by applying the AI embedded sensor ISM330DHCX [17] for mechanical fault detection in high voltage electric motor of Connected Electric Truck powertrain.

III. METHODOLOGY

We conducted five experiments to develop and validate a novel fault detection system using the ISM330DHCX for rotor unbalance detection in Connected Electric Truck powertrain.

A. Sensor Integration: ISM330DHCX with MLC

Fig. 3: Sensor Tile Wireless Industrial Node Development Kit (STWIN) and embedded ISM330DHCX IMU Sensor [17].

In line with above findings, benchmarking of several off-the-shelf solution containing ISM330DHCX sensor was done considering the ease of use and plug-and-play capability. As a result, the Sensor Tile Wireless Industrial Node Development Kit (STWIN) from STMicroelectronics, shown in Fig. 3 was selected. STWIN is a small multi-sensing electronic board featuring an ARM microcontroller and nine non-invasive sensors including ISM330DHCX which is an ultra-low powered system-in-package MEMS sensor featuring a high-performance 3D digital accelerometer and 3D digital gyroscope with Machine Learning Core. It has 9 kbytes data buffering with the maximum current consumption of 1.5 mA in high-performance mode. The MLC uses Decision Trees (DT) for evaluations and thereby minimize energy use. There are 8 DTs in total and strategically using all the 8 DTs can lead to a Random Forest model [17].

B. Data Acquisition

The data acquisition from ISM330DHCX is used to develop DT and RF ML model for fault classification. STWIN was programmed for data logging using STM32CubeIDE. The sampling rate was configured at 104 Hz ODR with the corresponding sensitivities (accelerometer: 2g; gyroscope: 125 mdps). Data was acquired using STDATALOG PYSDK which is a comprehensive Python framework designed to facilitate the capture, processing, and visualization of data from a wide range of STMicroelectronics devices. The data was stored in DAT format and then converted into CSV format for ML model development programmed via UNICO-GUI [19]. Using Unico-GUI application can enable simulation of STM boards like ISM330DHCX providing fast and reliable ML model training based on DTs. By providing the acquired data from different on-device sensors with its correct labels and configuring learning parameters of the model (i.e. classes needed, number of DTs), Unico-GUI test hundreds of pre-build models and choose the most suitable based on the highest accuracy obtained; each DT of the resultant model has been configured through its parameters for obtaining the maximum

accuracy ratio for each class using the real data acquired from the truck and selecting the best fault-detection features. Features including peak-to-peak, energy, etc. were extracted from the raw data for the model training and development. The developed ML model (UCF file) is deployed in ISM330DHCX using the STDATALOG PYSDK GUI application and outputs update every 0.5 s (52-sample window at 104 Hz).

C. Experimental Progression

Initially only two sets of experiments had to be performed. One for acquiring data to build the ML model and another one to validate the model. However, at the end 5 different experiments were performed as listed in Table I and in each experiment 3 tests were performed to simulate normal mode, warning mode and failure mode as listed in Table III.

TABLE I: Description of the different experiments.

Exp. No.	Name	Description
1	Single-DT Model Development	Developed a single-DT model for three operational classes (No Load, Low Load, Heavy Load), achieving 95% training accuracy.
2	Single-DT Validation	Validated the single-DT model, yielding <50% validation accuracy due to overlapping vibration patterns.
3	Extend Data Collection and New Model	Collected additional data, developing a new single-DT model with 96% training accuracy.
4	New Single-DT Validation	Validated the new single-DT model with more data, achieving 98.42% training accuracy but <50% validation accuracy.
5	Eight-DT as Random Forest Development and Validation	Developed an eight-DT RF model using data from the 3rd and 4th experiments, splitting each operational class into four modes (stopped, acceleration, constant, deceleration), creating 12 subclasses (Table II).

D. MLC Setup and Random Forest Configuration

The ISM330DHCX MLC, configured via Unico-GUI v9.17.2.0, employs up to eight DTs to process accelerometer and gyroscope data, extracting features such as `F39_ZeroCross_on_ACC_Z` (zero-crossing rate on the Z-axis) and other vibration-derived descriptors. The configuration is stored in a Unico Configuration File (UCF), a text-based file containing register write operations that can be converted into C-header files for integration into firmware. The UCF defines DT node thresholds, leaf assignments, and the Lookup Table (LUT) that maps DT outputs to runtime values. The ISM330DHCX MLC was configured with DTs from the training dataset as shown in Table II i.e. DT0 has 12 leaves with 0='NLA', 4='HLA', 8='LLA', constrained by the hardware limits of 128 nodes and 64 leaves. Each DT produces a leaf output (MLC0–MLC8 or DT0–DT7), which is mapped via a LUT into an 8-bit integer register (MLC8/DT8). This 8-bit value represents the runtime observable output and may be interpreted as signed (–128 to 127) or unsigned (0 to 255), depending on firmware configuration. Only DT8 is available at runtime, while decoding into primary load classes (No Load, Low Load, Heavy Load) occurs externally at the gateway or cloud as highlighted in Fig. 1 and Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: MLC pipeline.

E. Subclass Splitting and Output Mapping

An electric motor operates in four fundamental modes i.e. acceleration, deceleration, constant speed and stopped, as validated in Fig. 6. The 12-subclass splitting strategy as described in Table II maps these modes into No Load (NLA, NLC, NLD, NLS), Low Load (LLA, LLC, LLD, LLS) and Heavy Load (HLA, HLC, HLD, HLS), representing baseline, warning, and failure conditions. The DT outputs capture subtle vibration signatures like high-frequency dynamics in acceleration (e.g., NLA), steady patterns in constant speed (e.g., NLC), reduced amplitudes in deceleration (e.g., NLD) and idle states in stopped conditions (e.g., NLS), as shown in Fig. 7. These outputs are mapped through the LUT into the 8-bit MLC8/DT8 values, which are used in validation to represent these 12 subclasses as shown in Table II.

TABLE II: Mapping of 12 subclasses to 8 DT outputs.

Class	DT0	DT1	DT2	DT3	DT4	DT5	DT6	DT7
NLA	0	0	-	-	-	-	-	0
NLC	1	1	-	-	-	-	0	-
NLD	2	2	-	-	-	0	-	-
NLS	3	3	-	-	0	-	-	-
HLA	4	-	0	-	-	-	-	1
HLC	5	-	1	-	-	-	1	-
HLD	6	-	2	-	-	1	-	-
HLS	7	-	3	-	1	-	-	-
LLA	8	-	-	0	-	-	-	2
LLC	9	-	-	1	-	-	2	-
LLD	10	-	-	2	-	2	-	-
LLS	11	-	-	3	2	-	-	-

***Legend:** Numbers indicate the leaf code assigned by that DT for each class. “-” indicates no contribution. NL = No Load, LL = Low Load, HL = High Load; A = Acceleration, D = Deceleration, C = Constant, S = Stopped.

An eight-DT RF model, trained on vibration signature datasets, distributes sensitivity across the trees, ensuring robust classification within hardware constraints. The configuration ensures that each DT tuple maps consistently to MLC8/DT8, but overlapping vibration signatures introduce minor ambiguity and some integers may correspond to multiple subclasses leading to false positives. However, this is a tradeoff that should be considered taken into account the hardware constraints and its significant advantages.

Fig. 5: Measurement setup.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Experiments were conducted at Austrian Institute of Technology lab, simulating rotor unbalance on the RHODAS motor, with the STWIN mounted on the stator. The electric motor in the RHODAS project is provided by Valeo e-Automotive company. The high-voltage electric motor is designed for advanced traction applications, featuring a maximum operating speed of 10,500 rpm and a DC bus voltage capability up to 950 V. With an inverter current of 173 Arms, it provides 191 Nm continuous torque and 183 kW rated power, while maintaining a phase-to-phase voltage of 640 V. The motor supports switching frequencies up to 50 kHz and is rated for Class H insulation, tolerating winding temperatures up to 180 °C and ambient conditions from -20 °C to 50 °C. High efficiency is ensured through excellent power factor values (0.92 at 8400 rpm, 0.9962 at 10,500 rpm), with durability validated for 500 hours of continuous operation [5].

Rotor unbalance due to ageing, accident or manufacturing defect could lead to vibrations which can destroy the drivetrain. To simulate such an unbalance in rotation different weights of 28 g and 72 g were added on the motor shaft as shown in Fig. 5. For all the experiments STWIN was mounted with Pattex mounting adhesive on top of the stator. To achieve a better connection to the stator housing a masking tape was applied beforehand. Fig. 5 shows the measurement setup for all the experiments. Test bench measurements include speed (Fig. 6) and torque of the electrical motor with respect to time which were measured with the help of a torque measurement shaft from Kistler.

Table I provides the objectives and requirements of five experiments. In each experiment, three operational conditions were executed to emulate normal, warning, and failure modes, corresponding to no load, low load, and high load, respectively. The no load condition was realized with no additional weight on the motor shaft, the low load condition with 28 g attached, and the high load condition with 72 g attached. Data logging from the STWIN and test bench measurements were well coordinated and synchronised. The test procedure was divided into four sections as highlighted in Fig. 6:

1. Time to start delay.
2. Ramp up to 5000 rpm.
3. Constant speed at 5000 rpm.
4. Turn off the motor (rotor rotates freely).

The time in each section was different between experiment set (1,2) and experiment set (3,4,5) as highlighted in Table III.

TABLE III: Test matrix of the experiments.

Condition	Exp. 1,2	Exp 3,4,5
No load: Normal mode	delay 1 s – Ramp up to 5000 rpm in 20 s – 20 s constant speed – turn off	delay 5 s – Ramp up to 5000 rpm in 45 s – 120 s constant speed – turn off in 280 s
Low load (28 g): Warning mode	delay 1 s – Ramp up to 5000 rpm in 20 s – 20 s constant speed – turn off	delay 5 s – Ramp up to 5000 rpm in 45 s – 120 s constant speed – turn off in 280 s
High load (72 g): Failure mode	delay 1 s – Ramp up to 5000 rpm in 20 s – 20 s constant speed – turn off	delay 5 s – Ramp up to 5000 rpm in 45 s – 120 s constant speed – turn off in 280 s

Fig. 6: Test procedure for the experiments.

Fig. 7: Comparison on the X-axis accelerometer data.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As illustrated in Fig. 7, fault detection is straightforward under constant-speed conditions, where normal and faulty states can be reliably distinguished using simple rule-based or threshold-based methods. In contrast, during acceleration or deceleration, differentiating between Low Load and Heavy Load conditions is more challenging, as the corresponding signals exhibit high similarity. Applying the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) enables the identification of resonance phenomena and facilitates more accurate fault classification. However, the selected approach must remain compatible with time-domain analysis and support implementation through a decision tree model on the ISM330DHCX sensor’s MLC, as all processing is executed locally within the sensor.

A. Single-DT Models (Experiments 1-4)

The single-DT model in the 1st experiment achieved 95% training accuracy but <50% validation accuracy on 2nd experiment. The 3rd experiment’s new single-DT model reached 96% training accuracy, and the 4th experiment’s model hit 98.42% training accuracy, yet both maintained <50% validation accuracy due to overlapping vibration patterns in transitional modes (e.g., acceleration vs. stable). As the model was trained only to detect the three classes of No load, Low load and High load.

B. Eight-DT Random Forest Model (Experiment 5)

The RHODAS project’s eight-DT Random Forest model, trained on vibration data from the 3rd and 4th experiments,

was validated in Experiment 5. The ISM330DHCX MLC produced 12 subclass outputs (NLA, NLC, NLD, NLS, HLA, HLC, HLD, HLS, LLA, LLC, LLD, LLS), with their DT assignments configured as shown in Table II and detailed outputs listed in Table IV. The MLC produced DT outputs, which were mapped via the LUT to integer outputs (MLC8/DT8): -117, 11, 0, 9, 65, 95. During validation, duplicate DT tuples were observed across subclasses, reflecting aggregated vibration patterns from multiple experiments as shown in Table IV. Stopped conditions (NLS, LLS, HLS) consistently map to 0, overlapping with Low Load Acceleration (LLA). Another overlapping conditions (NLD, HLC) maps to 65. These overlap introduces potential false positives when only a single MLC8/DT8 reading is observed. At runtime, however, each DT tuple maps to a unique integer, and external decoding converts DT8 into the primary load classes. Excluding stopped conditions, nine active subclasses (NLA, NLC, NLD, HLA, HLC, HLD, LLA, LLC, LLD) were analyzed, with LLA at 0 remaining uniquely identifiable. These integers were then decoded externally into primary load classes: No Load (65, 95), Low Load (0, 9) and Heavy Load (-117, 11) as summarized in Table V.

TABLE IV: Subclass and Output mapping.

Sub-class	DT 0	DT 1	DT 2	DT 3	DT 4	DT 5	DT 6	DT 7	DT 8	Main class
NLA	7	3	3	3	1	1	2	1	95	NL
NLC	6	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	95	NL
NLD	8	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	65	NL
NLS	6	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	NL
HLA	8	0	2	0	2	2	0	2	11	HL
HLC	10	0	2	0	2	2	1	2	65	HL
HLD	6	2	2	0	2	1	1	1	-117	HL
HLS	10	2	2	2	2	2	0	2	0	HL
LLA	6	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	LL
LLC	8	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	9	LL
LLD	8	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	9	LL
LLS	6	2	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	LL

***Legend:** DT0–DT7 = decision tree leaf outputs. DT8 = LUT-mapped signed/unsigned integer. Main class = decoded class (NL = No Load, LL = Low Load, HL = Heavy Load).

Fig. 8: Confusion Matrix of the 8-DT RF model.

The model achieved a validation accuracy of 98.74%, with per-class accuracies of 100% (No Load), 99% (Low Load) and 97% (Heavy Load) as summarized in Table V. The

overall reduction from 100% accuracy is primarily due to: 1) ambiguous integers caused by overlapping DT outputs in validation, and 2) the stopped-state overlap with moving states like LLA. Subclass splitting and multiple test sections improved the model's ability to distinguish subtle vibration patterns, contributing to strong generalization and robust real-time performance, as depicted in Fig. 8. Mitigation strategies such as temporal smoothing or sliding-window majority voting can further reduce false positives in runtime applications.

TABLE V: Results of the 8-DT RF model.

Condition / Class	MLC Outputs	Accuracy (%)
Overall	N/A	98.74
No Load	(65, 95)	100
Low Load	(0, 9)	99
Heavy Load	(-117, 11)	97

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented an on-sensor fault detection system based on the ISM330DHCX MLC for real-time identification of vibration anomalies in critical operational states, such as High Load Stable (HLS) and High Load Deceleration (HLD). By detecting faults at the “P” (Potential Failure) point of the DIPF curve, the system enables early intervention and supports proactive maintenance strategies, thereby improving the reliability of Connected Electric Truck powertrain. The proposed on-sensor Random Forest model, incorporating eight-DT, 12 subclass splits, and a tailored prediction-to-class mapping, achieved a validation accuracy of 98.74%, substantially outperforming single-DT approaches. This design effectively captures dynamic operational modes while optimizing microcontroller resources, demonstrating the feasibility of low-power, real-time predictive maintenance at the sensor level. This work introduces a practical and efficient approach to on-sensor fault detection in automotive applications. By addressing latency and energy limitations inherent in cloud-based solutions, the proposed method advances the development of reliable, resource-aware predictive maintenance AI sensor network systems for electric vehicles. Future work would involve incorporating MLC into an ultrasound sensor, as ultrasound sensors, according to the DIPF curve, are capable of detecting failure signatures earlier than accelerometers.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the project name Reinventing High-performance pOwer converters for heavy-Duty electric trAnSport (RHODAS) and grant agreement No 101056896.

DISCLAIMER: This document reflects the view of its author(s) only. Neither the European Commission nor the

funding agency are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zhao, S. Peyghami, D. Gebbran, T. Dragicevic, H. Wang, and F. Blaabjerg, “Artificial intelligence and long-term performance of power electronics systems,” in *Proceedings of the CIPS 2022; 12th International Conference on Integrated Power Electronics Systems*, vol. 2022-March. VDE Verlag GMBH, Mar. 2022, pp. 5–14.
- [2] R. K. Mobley, *An introduction to predictive maintenance*. Elsevier, 2002.
- [3] RHODAS. (2022). [Online]. Available: <https://www.rhodas.eu/>
- [4] E. Armengaud, I. Armengaud, M. Weinzerl, J. Kniewallner, B. Brandstaetter, M. Cusic, A. Sornioti, K. M. So, U. Montanaro, L. Romeral *et al.*, “E-volve cluster: Increasing innovation efficiency to support the transition toward sustainable e-mobility,” in *Transport Research Arena Conference*. Springer, 2024, pp. 558–564.
- [5] D. Lumberas, “System specifications and requirements for electric and electronic system including thermal management system,” Jan. 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10254608>
- [6] B. Poudel and A. Munir, “Design and evaluation of a reconfigurable ecu architecture for secure and dependable automotive cps,” *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 235–252, 2018.
- [7] A. Kadechkar, J.-R. Riba, M. Moreno-Eguilaz, F. Capelli, and D. González, “On-line resistance measurement of substation connectors focused on predictive maintenance,” in *2018 IEEE 18th International Power Electronics and Motion Control Conference (PEMC)*, 2018, pp. 846–851.
- [8] F. Naseri, S. Gil, C. Barbu, E. Cetkin, G. Yarimca, A. Jensen, P. Larsen, and C. Gomes, “Digital twin of electric vehicle battery systems: Comprehensive review of the use cases, requirements, and platforms,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 179, p. 113280, 2023.
- [9] K. Sathupadi, S. Achar, S. V. Bhaskaran, N. Faruqui, M. Abdullah-Al-Wadud, and J. Uddin, “Edge-cloud synergy for ai-enhanced sensor network data: A real-time predictive maintenance framework,” *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 24, 2024.
- [10] I. ISO, “17359: 2018—condition monitoring and diagnostics of machines—general guidelines,” *ISO: Geneva, Switzerland*, 2018.
- [11] D. Shi, G. Feng, X. Du, Z. Zhou, F. Gu, and A. D. Ball, “The design and fabrication of an on-rotor sensing wireless vibration node for motor condition monitoring,” *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 73, pp. 1–11, 2024.
- [12] A. Kadechkar, J.-R. Riba, G. Rojas-Dueñas, J. A. Martinez, and M. Moreno-Eguilaz, “Experimental study of the effect of aeolian vibrations on the contact resistance of substation connectors,” in *2020 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Technology (ICIT)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 613–618.
- [13] M. Brehler, L. Camphausen, B. Heidebroek, D. Krön, H. Gründer, and S. Camphausen, “Making machine learning more energy efficient by bringing it closer to the sensor,” *IEEE micro*, vol. 43, no. 6, pp. 11–18, 2023.
- [14] E. Parisi, A. Moallemi, F. Barchi, A. Bartolini, D. Brunelli, N. Buratti, and A. Acquaviva, “Time and frequency domain assessment of low-power mems accelerometers for structural health monitoring,” in *2022 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Industry 4.0 & IoT (MetroInd4.0&IoT)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 234–239.
- [15] L. Bibbò, G. Angiulli, F. Laganà, D. Praticò, F. Cotroneo, F. La Foresta, and M. Versaci, “Mems and iot in har: Effective monitoring for the health of older people,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 15, no. 8, p. 4306, 2025.
- [16] O. Vermesan and M. Coppola, “Edge ai platforms for predictive maintenance in industrial applications,” in *Embedded Artificial Intelligence*. River Publishers, 2023, pp. 89–104.
- [17] A. N. A. STMicroelectronics, “Ism330dhcx: machine learning core.”
- [18] O. Vermesan and M. Coppola, “Embedded edge intelligent processing for end-to-end predictive maintenance in industrial applications,” in *Industrial Artificial Intelligence Technologies and Applications*. River Publishers, 2023, pp. 157–175.
- [19] Y. Uchida, E. Ohkubo, and T. Funayama, “A proposal for an evaluation method of table slide exercise using a mems sensor,” in *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Sensors Engineering Electronics Instrumentation Advance (SEIA'24)*, 2024, pp. 59–62.